

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN LEARNING

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Abstract: This research article will discuss the main roles of motivation in learning something new. Besides, it will discuss some other ways of inspiring students for teachers, because without motivation students get depressed easily and it might affect the quality of their learning process. What ways should be taken into consideration when teaching and learning new subject.

Key words: motivation, different, children, education, energy, intellectual, set goals, develop interests, academic performance.

Introduction

Learning something new requires too much passion and hard work from every individual. People, who want to learn language, especially need motivation for their further academic skills. The higher motivation of students, the more fruitful will be the study of a foreign language. Based on the data of pragmalinguistics and taking into account the changed status of a foreign language as a means of communication and mutual understanding in the world community, the modern technique emphasize the need to strengthen the motivational aspects of language learning.

There are several definitions of motivation. Motivation has been related to the amount of intellectual energy typically used in learning activities, and this led to a belief that motivation could be seen as a stable characteristic of the individual, on a par with personality. Motivation is what causes a person wants to know, act, understand, believe or gain particular skills. Motivation can also be defined as the drive to satisfy the individual's need e.g. a learner who wants to learn how to read and count so that he/she won't be cheated when s/he goes out shopping. Other scholars have also defined motivation in several ways. The existence of this variety of definitions shows the difficulty in describing motivation and its role in the process of learning. Consequently, the first step is to clarify some of the problematic aspects of the term motivation as it described in Rodicio [55]: motivation is not a physical feature; that is, it cannot be observed directly. Madrid [56] explained the concept of motivation as an individual state that is influenced by different factors such as beliefs, interests, goals, and wishes that demand an effort from students.

Recently, other scholars have also added their voices. Spolsky [57] described motivation as the amount of time a learner is prepared to spend on learning tasks. Orgeta-Martin [58] explained that motivation is an individual's disposition to learning a task that can be modified both by himself or herself and by the surrounding circumstances. According to a Bhatia, motivation is the stimulation or action towards a particular goal where previously there was little or no attraction towards that goal (Bhatia, [59]). Cole [60] defined motivation as the internal state that instigates, directs, and maintains behavior. Furthermore, we could count many descriptions for motivation. According to Hannah Hawthorne [60]: Motivation is defined as our enthusiasm for doing something. It is the 'why' behind every action. Motivation is the reason – or reasons – for acting or behaving in a particular way. It helps us to set a goal

and reach it. The term 'motivation' is derived from the Latin verb 'movere', so quite literally, it's what keeps us moving.

In education, motivation helps children and young people to focus their attention on a key goal or outcome. In doing so, they are unfazed by possible distractions, and are therefore able to maintain their attention during longer periods of time. Students who are motivated display goal-orientated behaviours. They take initiative, show resilience, harness their curiosity, and care for and respect their work. They are equipped to orchestrate their own learning journey.

Discovering ways to increase motivation in the classroom is vital, as it enables us to:

Change behaviour.

Develop competencies.

Spark curiosity.

Set goals.

Develop interests.

Plan for the future.

Blossom talents.

Increase engagement.

Getting students engaged in a lesson or unit of work is something a talented teacher can achieve, but motivating them to become better learners, who strive to achieve their true potential, can be incredibly challenging, especially as our experience of motivation is often unconscious. Unmotivated students are often disengaged or disaffected, which can lead to challenging behavior.

Furthermore, there are some impacts of motivation on behavior and performance. Let's look at some of them which were explained by Hannah Hwthrone [61] Motivation pushes children to work hard and aim high in everything they set their minds to. When students are surrounded by a culture of warmth, diversity, and high expectations, they are much more likely to display positive behaviours. Children who are motivated are also more likely to find pleasure in satisfying their academic curiosity. Intrinsic motivation links strongly to performance merely for the enjoyment of engaging in activities. This pleasure is often the reason that pupils take part in academic tasks.

How Motivation Affects Academic Performance

We know that students who are intrinsically motivated are much more likely to be successful in their education, but can extrinsic motivation help to improve performance?

In a research project run by the Education Endowment Foundation, students in KS4 were offered an incentive for achieving their set GCSE targets. Participants were extrinsically motivated through either a financial reward, or access to a paid trip. Where students were offered a monetary incentive, there was a significant improvement in classwork effort seen within English, maths, and science. However, there was no evidence of a significant positive impact on attainment. Therefore, extrinsic motivation can prove to be successful in improving engagement, but as this study proves, there is limited evidence to suggest that it boosts attainment, or would help to maintain effort over a long period of time.

Enjoyment in lessons has been found to be strongly linked to high levels of student motivation. Studies assessing motivation in physical education found that enjoyment is a valuable predictor of two situations – a child's willingness to begin a physical activity, and how long they will maintain it once it's begun (Navarro-Patón, 2018). When students have fun

and find success, they experience improved self-worth and self-belief, which are key drivers in developing a self-summoned desire to achieve.

Similarly, when assessing pedagogy in physical education, a Public Health study found that class settings, a sense of connectedness, and social dynamics need to be considered if educators are to enhance pupils' motivation, self-determination, and engagement (Lamb and Kirk, 2021). It also found that developing pedagogies which support young people's mental health and wellbeing and improving relationships with teachers were key motivating factors in pupils' engagement in the subject.

Conclusion

Even there are many definitions of motivation I consider that real motivation is in the hearts of every child who wants to learn something new. Weather it is language or any kind of subject. While learning new aspects of something, if the children have passion and motivation for that they will definitely acquire knowledge for lifelong.

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